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Efficacy and Safety of Chia Seed Powder, Pea Protein, and Xyloglucan in Patients with Constipation-Predominant Irritable Bowel Syndrome: A Multicenter, Double-Blind, Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Trial

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Academic Editors: Andrew Day and Michio Hongo

Received: 22 January 2025

Revised: 11 February 2025

Accepted: 20 February 2025

Published: 23 February 2025

Citation: Armova, M.; Nikolova, M.S.; Draganov, P.M.; Peneva, P.V.; Sabaté, J.M.; Santos, J. Efficacy and Safety of Chia Seed Powder, Pea Protein, and Xyloglucan in Patients with Constipation-Predominant Irritable Bowel Syndrome: A Multicenter, Double-Blind, Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Trial.

Gastrointest. Disord. **2025**, *7*, 19.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/gidisord7010019>

gidisord7010019

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Abstract: Background/Objectives: Natural compounds represent novel promising alternative treatments for functional gastrointestinal disorders. This multicenter, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled, crossover study aimed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of xyloglucan, pea protein, and chia seed powder (XP + CS) in irritable bowel syndrome with constipation (IBS-C). Methods: Sixty patients received twice-daily XP + CS or placebo for 28 days. Following a 28-day washout period, patients switched to the alternative treatment for another 28 days. Efficacy was evaluated using the Bristol Stool Form Scale; a seven-point Likert scale for abdominal pain, bloating, and discomfort; a Visual Analogue Scale for IBS symptom severity; the quality of life (QoL)-IBS questionnaire; Sickness Impact Profile (SIP) score; and serum zonulin concentrations. Adverse events were monitored throughout the study. Results: Compared to the placebo, XP + CS significantly improved stool consistency ($p = 0.04$ and $p < 0.001$ at days 15 and 28, respectively), IBS symptoms ($p < 0.001$ at day 15), QoL ($p < 0.001$ from day 15 on), and nearly all SIP domains ($p < 0.001$ at all time-points). Additionally, XP + CS treatment restored serum zonulin concentrations to within normal ranges by day 15. No serious adverse events were reported. Conclusions: This study provides evidence supporting the efficacy and safety of XP + CS in managing IBS-C symptoms.

Keywords: irritable bowel syndrome; constipation; xyloglucan; pea protein; chia seed powder

1. Introduction

Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is a functional bowel disorder classified among the Disorders of Gut–Brain Interaction (DGBI), characterized by recurrent abdominal pain and impaired bowel habits in the absence of a detectable organic cause [1]. IBS affects approximately 4–10% of the global population [2]. A subset of IBS, IBS with constipation

(IBS-C), accounts for about 30% of IBS cases. IBS-C encompasses the general symptoms of IBS, including chronic or recurrent abdominal pain and bloating, alongside constipation-specific features such as hard stools and reduced intestinal motility [3]. These symptoms significantly impact patients' quality of life (QoL) [4].

The pathophysiology of IBS-C remains incompletely understood but is considered heterogeneous and multifactorial. Recently, the gut barrier has emerged as a key area of interest, with studies reporting intestinal epithelial dysfunction and increased intestinal paracellular permeability in several gastrointestinal (GI) disorders [5,6]. These findings suggest that a compromised intestinal barrier may allow transepithelial antigen diffusion, triggering immune responses [5]. Although further evidence is needed to confirm the presence of altered intestinal permeability specifically in IBS-C patients, improving gut barrier function could represent a promising therapeutic target for various GI disorders, including IBS [7].

The management of IBS-C includes a variety of pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatments, such as laxatives, prokinetics and prosecretory agents, prebiotics, and probiotics [3,8–10]. However, many IBS-C patients remain dissatisfied with these options, with 50% reporting a lack of efficacy and 40% experiencing side effects [11,12]. Recently, natural substances have gained attention as potential treatments for constipation. Compounds such as yellow tea extract and short-chain fatty acids have shown the ability to alleviate constipation by enhancing intestinal transit and improving fecal water content [13,14]. Similarly, certain muco-protective agents exhibit promising effects: xyloglucan (XG), or tamarind seed polysaccharide, strengthens the intestinal mucosa and restores physiological intestinal functions [15,16], while pea protein (PP) from *Pisum sativum* exerts emollient and soothing actions on the digestive tract and improves gut mucosal barrier functions [17,18]. Finally, chia seed powder (CS) from *Salvia hispanica* acts as a natural bulking agent, accelerating intestinal transit [19].

The effects of the combination of XG and PP (XP) have previously been evaluated in preclinical studies, where XP normalized intestinal permeability and reduced visceral hypersensitivity in a model of partial restraint stress [20]. Additionally, two clinical studies demonstrated that XP is safe and effective in alleviating all gastrointestinal symptoms associated with IBS-D [15,21]. These findings were corroborated by two further studies, confirming the efficacy of XP in managing IBS symptoms [22,23]. Recently, the combination of XP with CS (XP + CS) was investigated in a rat model of IBS-C, where it preserved intestinal integrity and functionality, ultimately improving constipation-related symptoms [24]. These findings suggest that the combined effects of these natural substances may effectively and safely manage IBS-C symptoms.

The aim of this clinical study was to evaluate the efficacy and safety of the combination of two muco-protective agents with a natural laxative in IBS-C patients.

2. Results

2.1. Demographics and Baseline Clinical Characteristics

A total of 60 patients were randomized in a 1:1 ratio into two groups to receive either XP + CS (Group 1) or placebo (Group 2) for 28 days (Period 1). Demographic and clinical data at baseline are reported in Table 1, demonstrating no statistically significant differences between groups.

2.2. Efficacy Results

2.2.1. Stool Consistency

All 60 patients reported constipation at baseline, as assessed by the Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS) (Figure 1). Overall, XP + CS was superior to the placebo in resolving constipa-

tion. At day 28 (Period 1), all patients in group 1 reported a score of 3–5 (normal stools), whereas all patients in Group 2 reported a score of 1–2 (constipation). Furthermore, patients treated with XP + CS showed significant improvements in stool consistency compared to the placebo at both day 15 ($p = 0.04$) and 28 ($p < 0.001$). The remission rate in Group 1 was 46.7% at day 15 and 100% at day 28, compared to 16.7% and 0%, respectively, in Group 2 (Figure 1 and Supplementary Figure S1). Similar trends were observed in Period 2, with a statistically significant difference in stool consistency between groups at day 84 ($p < 0.001$), further demonstrating the superior efficacy of XP + CS. Notably, no patient reported a Bristol score of 6–7 (diarrhea) at any timepoint. Full data and statistics are provided in Supplementary Table S1.

Table 1. Demographic and clinical data at baseline.

	Group 1 XP + CS/Placebo <i>n</i> = 30	Group 2 Placebo/XP + CS <i>n</i> = 30	<i>p</i> Value
Gender M:F, <i>n</i> (%)	18 (60.0):12 (40.0)	16 (53.3):14 (46.7)	0.79
Age (years), mean (SD)	35.7 (10.5)	35.5 (11.7)	0.76
Height (cm), mean (SD)	169.1 (7.7)	169.2 (9.8)	0.95
Weight (kg), mean (SD)	77.3 (13.3)	77.3 (14.0)	0.99
BMI (kg/m ²), mean (SD)	25.7 (3.1)	26.7 (3.0)	1.00
IBS symptoms ^a , mean (SD)			
Discomfort	2.17 (0.83)	2.40 (0.89)	1.00
Bloating	2.27 (0.74)	2.20 (0.71)	1.00
Abdominal pain	2.73 (1.11)	3.07 (0.94)	1.00
Serum zonulin (ng/mL), mean (SD)	60.8 (13.0)	63.9 (15.5)	1.00
IBS QoL score ^b , mean (SD)	59.9 (11.7)	55.7 (11.2)	1.00

XP + CS = xyloglucan pea protein + chia seed powder; M = male; F = female; SD = standard deviation; BMI = body mass index; IBS = irritable bowel syndrome; IBS QoL = IBS quality of life questionnaire. *p* values were calculated using unpaired *t*-tests or Wilcoxon tests (as appropriate) for continuous variables. Fisher’s exact test was used for gender. ^a Likert scale: 7-point scale from 1 (totally unacceptable) to 7 (perfectly acceptable). ^b IBS-QoL individual scores are transformed to a 0–100 scale, with higher scores indicating a better quality of life.

Figure 1. Improvement in stool consistency. Treatment with XP + CS significantly increased the percentage of patients with normal stools, while placebo showed no effect in reducing constipation. Patients with constipation are represented in orange (Stool Bristol type 1–2), and those with normal stools (Stool Bristol type 3–5) are represented in blue. No patients presented diarrhea (Stool Bristol type 6–7).

2.2.2. IBS Symptoms

At baseline, all IBS symptoms (i.e., abdominal pain, bloating, and discomfort) were averagely rated as “unacceptable” on a 7-point Likert scale (Table 1). Overall, XP + CS treatment demonstrated significantly greater efficacy in reducing symptoms compared to the placebo (Figure 2 and Supplementary Figure S2) at both day 15 ($p < 0.001$) and 28 ($p < 0.001$). In Group 1, a significant improvement in symptoms was observed as early as day 7 compared to baseline (bloating $p < 0.001$, abdominal pain $p = 0.007$, discomfort $p < 0.001$). Further improvement in Group 1 was recorded at day 15 and day 28, with all symptoms showing significant reductions ($p < 0.001$ for all comparisons to baseline). At the end of the washout period (day 56), no significant differences in symptoms were observed between groups. In Period 2, a similar significant improvement of all symptoms was observed in Group 2 ($p < 0.001$ for each comparison): at day 84, Group 2 showed a greater improvement in symptoms compared to Group 1 ($p < 0.001$ for each comparison). Of note, 30 days after the End of Treatment (EoT, day 114), significant differences in bloating and discomfort were observed between the groups ($p < 0.001$ for each comparison), possibly indicating a potential carry-over effect of XP + CS. However, this difference was not observed 60 days after the EoT (day 144). These findings were further supported by the Visual Analogue Scale for IBS (VAS-IBS) questionnaire outcomes, which evaluated symptoms and well-being (pain, bloating, flatulence, constipation, GI symptoms, psychological well-being, vomiting and nausea, diarrhea) on a 1–100 scale. XP + CS demonstrated overall superiority versus the placebo (Supplementary Table S2); specifically, Group 1 showed a significant improvement in symptoms compared to Group 2 as early as day 6 ($p < 0.05$). XP + CS was significantly superior to the placebo at days 15, 28, and 84 ($p < 0.001$ for all comparisons) across all endpoints analyzed.

2.2.3. Serum Zonulin

At baseline, a mean serum zonulin concentration above the normal range (20.0–48.0 ng/mL) was detected in both groups, suggesting possible intestinal hyperpermeability. At day 28, only patients treated with XP + CS showed a significant reduction in serum zonulin concentration, reaching values within the normal range ($p < 0.001$). After washout (day 56), zonulin concentration was over normal values in both groups. At the end of Period 2 (day 84), patients treated with XP + CS exhibited significantly lower zonulin levels compared to day 56 ($p < 0.001$). Statistically significant differences between groups were observed at day 15 ($p < 0.001$), day 28 ($p < 0.001$), and day 84 ($p < 0.001$), highlighting XP + CS's ability to restore serum zonulin levels (Figure 3).

To investigate the relationship between serum zonulin levels and constipation, a correlation analysis was performed. A significant, albeit weak, correlation was found between VAS-IBS constipation scores and serum zonulin concentrations at each visit from day 0 to day 84 (overall $r^2 = 0.232$, $p < 0.001$), except at day 56 ($r^2 = 0.018$, $p = 0.31$) (Supplementary Figure S3). Linear regression analysis further confirmed a significant inverse relationship between the two variables (overall slope = -0.75 , $p < 0.001$), except at day 56 (slope = 0.25 , $p = 0.31$). The wide scatter observed justifies the weak correlation between the two variables.

2.2.4. Quality of Life (QoL)

QoL was significantly improved in patients treated with XP + CS compared to the placebo (Figure 4). In Group 1, the mean IBS-QoL score showed a significant increase at day 28 (Period 1) compared to baseline ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, in Period 2, patients in Group 2 reported significant improvement at day 84 compared to day 56 ($p < 0.001$). A significant difference between the groups was observed at days 15, 28, 84, and 114

($p < 0.001$ for each comparison), indicating an improvement in patient's QoL associated with XP + CS treatment.

Figure 2. Improvement in IBS symptoms assessed using a 7-point Likert scale (1 = totally unacceptable; 7 = perfectly acceptable). XP + CS treatment significantly reduced abdominal pain (a), bloating (b), and discomfort (c) in IBS-C patients. *** $p < 0.001$ vs. alternative arm.

Figure 3. Concentration of serum zonulin in IBS-C patients. Treatment with XP + CS significantly reduced serum zonulin levels, indicating an improvement in intestinal barrier function. Dashed lines mark the lower (20 ng/mL) and upper (48 ng/mL) limits of the normal serum zonulin concentration range. Values above 48 ng/mL indicate increased intestinal permeability. *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 4. Quality of life (QoL) in IBS-C patients. Treatment with XP + CS significantly improved QoL of IBS-C patients. *** $p < 0.001$ and ** $p < 0.01$ vs. alternative arm.

2.2.5. Sickness Impact Profile (SIP)

The Sickness Impact Profile (SIP) is a tool to assess patients’ perception of their health status with respect to a specific disease. In Group 1, all six items of the SIP showed a decrease at day 28 compared to baseline (Period 1) (Supplementary Table S3). When comparing the two groups, all SIP scores—except for the emotional stability domain—were significantly lower in the XP + CS group at each time-point ($p < 0.001$ for each comparison), indicating an improvement in health status with XP + CS treatment.

2.3. Safety Results

No serious adverse events (AEs) were reported during the study. A total of eight non-serious AEs were recorded in patients taking concomitant medications: five during placebo administration and three during XP + CS treatment. All of these were known AEs

associated with the concomitant medications (Table 2). No allergic reactions to the product were observed, and no patients withdrew from the study or discontinued the treatment. Adherence to therapy was optimal in both groups.

Table 2. Adverse events (AEs) reported by patients during the investigation period. Concomitant medications are indicated.

Treatment	Concomitant Medication	Symptoms	Nr. AE	Type
XP + CS	Nebivolol 5mg oral; Lisinopril 10 mg, oral; Vinpocetine 5 mg, oral Tamsulosin/Dutasteride 0.4 mg/5 mg oral	Flatulence	1	Non-serious, mild
		Vomiting	2	Non-serious, mild
Placebo	Irbesartan/Hydrochlorothiazide 300 mg/12.5 mg, oral; Nifedipine 5 mg, oral; Molsidomin 2 mg, oral; Apixaban 5 mg; Perindopril/Indapamide 4 mg/1.25 mg oral Metformin 500 mg, oral Metoprolol Succinate 25 mg, Gliklaside 60 mg, oral	Flatulence	3	Non-serious, mild
		Nausea	1	Non-serious, mild
		Shortness of breath	1	Non-serious, mild

3. Discussion

This study demonstrated that XP + CS significantly improves abdominal pain, bloating, discomfort, and stool consistency in patients with IBS-C. Interestingly, XP + CS also led to a reduction in serum zonulin concentrations, suggesting a potential role in restoring intestinal barrier integrity and permeability, which may help reduce inflammation and associated symptoms. Additionally, XP + CS was shown to be a safe therapeutic option that significantly improved the QoL and psychological well-being of IBS-C patients.

Although IBS severity was not directly assessed, patients included in the study reported poor QoL at baseline, potentially indicating rather high IBS severity [25,26]. As a first-in-human study, additional timepoints—deviating from the canonical design of cross-over studies—were included to assess the onset of action of the product. Based on the evaluation of this secondary outcome, the positive effects of XP + CS on stool consistency, IBS symptoms, and patients' QoL were observed as early as 15 days from treatment onset.

Such results are particularly relevant in the context of IBS-C treatment, given that, despite the availability of several therapeutic options, both healthcare providers and patients report that most treatments remain ineffective in managing all disease-related symptoms and improving patients' QoL [8,27,28]. Some laxatives, for instance, may cause dehydration or diarrhea, or lead to electrolyte imbalances [29]. A large survey-based study found that approximately 70% of IBS-C patients use fiber treatments, but only 12% of patients and 6.3% of physicians report high levels of satisfaction with their effectiveness [28].

Fibers can vary significantly in terms of solubility, fermentability, and viscosity, leading to different effects along the gastrointestinal tract [30]. Some fibers are fermented by the microbiota, creating an osmotic load that accelerates intestinal transit [31–33]. Insoluble fibers stimulate intestinal transit by irritating the mucosa, which triggers the release of water and mucus and often worsens symptoms. This partially explains the low satisfaction rates associated with their use [27]. In contrast, soluble fibers, which are only partially fermented, retain large amounts of water and form mucilage, helping to normalize stool consistency and improve fecal hydration [30,34]. Chia seeds contain about 34–40% dietary fiber, with 5–10% of it being soluble and capable of forming mucilage [35]. This fiber content is higher than in other dietary products such as quinoa or flaxseed [36], which may contribute to the bulking effect of chia seeds in the intestine.

It is worth noting that this study demonstrated that XP + CS was effective in normalizing stool consistency without causing diarrhea or inducing side effects. While the clinical performance of XG and PP has been extensively investigated in the treatment of various gastrointestinal disorders [15,21–23,37,38], clinical evidence supporting the laxative properties of CS is more limited. However, the potential of CS in managing constipation-related symptoms was explored in a recent preclinical study [24], which ultimately supports the results presented here.

In addition to its effectiveness, the XP + CS treatment demonstrated a high level of safety. Indeed, the only recorded adverse events—three during XP + CS administration and five during placebo administration—were classified as mild and non-serious, and considered unrelated to the investigational treatment. Furthermore, XP + CS was well tolerated, with no patients dropping out of the trial.

Increased intestinal permeability, correlated with high serum zonulin levels [39], has previously been observed in IBS-D patients [40,41]. However, the link between altered intestinal permeability and IBS-C remains controversial [41,42]. In this study, a weak correlation between serum zonulin concentration and IBS symptoms (specifically constipation) was found. The results support the growing body of evidence suggesting that barrier dysfunction plays a key role in IBS-C pathophysiology. Recently, zonulin has gained attention as a marker for intestinal permeability, as it can easily be measured in patient serum. However, given the limitations of commercially available ELISA kits for serum zonulin quantification [43], it would be beneficial in the future to validate these findings using additional methods, such as the lactulose and mannitol assay (LMA), possibly leveraging the emerging potential of ¹³C mannitol [44]. Another limitation of this study is the absence of a severity assessment using the IBS Severity Scoring System (IBS-SSS), which would have provided a more robust insight into the severity and progression of IBS-C symptoms. Additionally, the patient population in this study had limited representativeness, as male patients were more prevalent. The small sample size further limits the generalizability of the findings. Moreover, the study relied solely on serum zonulin as the marker for intestinal barrier function, which may not fully capture the complexity of this process. To address these limitations, it will be important to confirm the promising results reported in this study through trials with larger sample sizes, longer follow-up periods, and the inclusion of more diverse populations. Further studies should also explore additional markers for intestinal dysfunction and use comprehensive severity scoring systems for a more complete assessment of treatment effects.

In conclusion, these results represent a first step in clinically proving the laxative effects of chia seeds. XP + CS-based therapy is safe, well tolerated, and effective in controlling constipation, abdominal pain, and bloating in IBS-C patients. Its proven efficacy in significantly improving patients' QoL represents a valuable solution for the management of the disease.

4. Materials and Methods

This multicenter, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled, crossover clinical trial was conducted in four gastroenterological medical centers in Bulgaria between May 2021 and August 2022. The study (NCT05240521 on [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov)) was approved by the relevant Ethical Committee on 26 May 2021 and was carried out in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki, the Good Clinical Practice guidelines, the ISO 14155:2020 [45], and the CPMP (CPMP/ICH/135/195; ICH Topic E6). Written informed consent was obtained from all patients.

Sixty patients diagnosed with IBS-C according to Rome IV criteria were enrolled. Patients were included if they (i) were over 18 years old; (ii) were willing to sign the

informed consent form; and (iii) were able to comply with investigation visits. Patients were excluded if they (i) were immunodeficient; (ii) had hypersensitivity to any of the ingredients of the product under investigation; (iii) were affected by chronic diarrhea caused by cystic fibrosis, coeliac disease, food allergies, diabetes, or lactose, fructose or sorbitol intolerance; (iv) had abnormal thyroid function, a history of alcohol abuse or binge drinking, pancreatitis, sphincter of Oddi dysfunction, or cholecystitis within the past 6 months; (v) used drugs or medical devices known to alter gastrointestinal motility or secretion within four weeks prior to enrolment (e.g., gelatine tannate, diosmectite, probiotics, racecadotril, or others); (vi) used prebiotics, fiber supplements, laxatives, 5-HT₄ agonists, antispasmodics, or anti-depressants within 4 weeks of the investigation baseline visit; or (vii) were pregnant or breast-feeding, or were planning to become pregnant or breastfeed during the study period.

Eligible subjects were randomized to receive XP + CS or placebo, with one capsule twice daily for 28 days (Period 1). After a 28-day washout period, designed to minimize any potential carryover effect, patients switched to the alternative treatment for another 28 days (Period 2). Patients were instructed not to make any changes to their lifestyle or dietary patterns during the study. The study flowchart is reported in Supplementary Figure S4.

The placebo was identical to the XP + CS treatment, but did not contain XG, PP, or CS, which were present only in the active treatment. Specifically, one capsule of XP + CS (identified on clinicaltrials.gov as GA-AT0119) contained 250 mg of chia seed powder, 175 mg of pea protein, and 100 mg of tamarind seed polysaccharide (xyloglucan). Excipients included magnesium stearate (vegetable origin) and silicon dioxide. Both the placebo and active treatment were supplied by Devintec SAGL (Lugano, Switzerland).

Treatment adherence, clinical symptoms, and safety were assessed over four visits during Period 1 at days 1, 7, 15, and 28, and over two visits during Period 2, at the end of the washout (day 56) and at the end of Period 2 (day 84). Visits at days 7 and 15 of Period 1 were scheduled to observe the onset of action of the product, as a secondary outcome of interest. Two additional follow-up visits were conducted at days 114 and 144 for safety reporting and the evaluation of clinical symptom recurrence.

Efficacy was assessed by evaluating the clinical remission rate, defined as the normalization of stool consistency (type 3–5 according to the Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS)) and bowel movements (more than 3 per week). Stool consistency was rated using the Bristol Stool Form Scale, which categorizes stools as follows: type 1, separate hard lumps, like nuts (difficult to pass); type 2, sausage-shaped, but lumpy; type 3, like a sausage but with cracks on its surface; type 4, like a sausage or snake, smooth and soft (normal stool); type 5, soft blobs with clear-cut edges; type 6, fluffy pieces with ragged edges, a mushy stool (diarrhea); type 7, watery, no solid pieces, entirely liquid (diarrhea). The individual stool-type ratings were classified as follows: stool types 1 and 2 represent constipation; types 3, 4, and 5 represent normal stool; and types 6 and 7 represent diarrhea.

Symptom evolution was evaluated using two different scales: subjective improvement of abdominal pain, bloating, and discomfort was assessed on a seven-point Likert scale (1 = totally unacceptable to 7 = perfectly acceptable), while a Visual Analogue Scale for IBS (VAS-IBS; 0 = extremely severe problems to 100 = absence of problems) was used to evaluate constipation, diarrhea, bloating and flatulence, vomiting and nausea, psychological well-being, and the impact of intestinal symptoms on daily life [46]. Additionally, the same symptoms were assessed daily during the first week of treatment using VAS-IBS.

The Irritable Bowel Syndrome Quality of Life (IBS-QoL) questionnaire, including 34 items, was used to record potential improvements in QoL. The individual responses were summed, averaged for a total score, and then transformed to a 0–100 scale, with higher scores indicating better QoL. The Sickness Impact Profile (SIP) score, a generic

behavioral-based measure of health status, was used to assess the subjective perception of health status. Specifically, SIP comprises six domains that assess physical, mental, and social aspects of health, with higher scores reflecting a worse health status [47].

In addition, mucosal barrier function was assessed by monitoring serum zonulin concentrations, a biomarker of mucosal barrier integrity, using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) [39].

Since the association between serum zonulin levels and IBS symptomatology is still a matter of debate, a correlation analysis with VAS-IBS was performed.

Finally, treatment safety and tolerability were monitored by tracking the occurrence of adverse events, allergic reactions to product administration, and the number of drop-outs due to side effects.

Statistical Analysis

The sample size was calculated based on subjective symptom improvement in abdominal pain score. Given that the expected change in pain score from baseline was approximately 0.49 for the placebo group, with a standard deviation of 0.27, and assuming a product effect of 0.21, a sample size of 54 subjects was calculated to be sufficient to detect the specified difference with at least 80% power and a 5% significance level. Considering a 10% drop-out rate, a minimum of 60 subjects was required to be included in the investigation.

Categorical variables were analyzed as counts and percentages, while continuous variables were reported as the mean and standard deviation (SD) or interquartile range (IR), as appropriate. The pooled or Satterthwaite version of the treatment and period differences was chosen based on the significance of the folded F-test for equal variances. A mixed model for repeated measures was used for the period from day 0 to day 7 with a compound symmetry covariance structure for VAS-IBS parameters, using treatment and baseline values as fixed effects. Patient ID was entered into the model as a random effect. Pairwise comparisons between days for VAS-IBS parameters were then adjusted for multiplicity using the Studentized Maximum Modulus method. The stepdown Bonferroni method was used for the exact F-test for within-day, between-treatment Bristol Scale comparisons. The one-sample proportion z-test, assuming normality, or the McNemar test was performed to assess the frequency distribution of within-treatment day comparisons. Pearson's correlation and linear regression analyses were conducted to test the association between the VAS-IBS constipation score and serum zonulin concentration. Scatterplots were produced with the VAS-IBS constipation score on the y-axis and serum zonulin concentration on the x-axis. All tests were two-tailed and considered significant at the 5% level. All analyses were conducted using SAS 9.4 (N.C. Cary USA).

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/gidisord7010019/s1>. Figure S1: Improvement in stool consistency during the first 15 days of treatment with XP+CS compared to placebo. Table S1: Bristol score summary statistics by days from randomization and treatment period. Figure S2: Number of patients reporting abdominal pain, bloating, and discomfort (corresponding to Likert values 1–4) according to a 7-point Likert scale (1 = totally unacceptable; 7 = perfectly acceptable). XP+CS treatment reduces the number of IBS-C patients reporting unacceptable levels of abdominal pain (a), bloating (b), and discomfort (c). Table S2: IBS VAS score summary statistics by days from randomization and treatment period. Figure S3: Correlation between the VAS-IBS score for constipation and the serum concentration of zonulin in IBS-C patients. Regression analysis plot by days from randomization. r^2 = Pearson's correlation coefficient. Table S3: SIP score summary statistics by days from randomization and treatment period. Figure S4: Study flowchart.

Author Contributions: Formal analysis, J.M.S. and J.S.; Investigation, M.A., M.S.N., P.M.D. and P.V.P.; Supervision, J.M.S. and J.S.; Writing—original draft, J.M.S. and J.S.; Writing—review and editing, M.A., M.S.N., P.M.D., P.V.P., J.M.S. and J.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This study was sponsored by Devintec SAGL, Switzerland.

Institutional Review Board Statement: This study (NCT05240521 in [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov)) was approved by the relevant Ethical Committee on 26 May 2021, and was carried out in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki, the Good Clinical Practice of the European Community, the ISO 14155:2020, and the CPMP (CPMP/ICH/135/195; ICH Topic E6).

Informed Consent Statement: Written informed consent was obtained from all patients.

Data Availability Statement: The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors on request.

Conflicts of Interest: J.M.S. reports personal fees from Devintec during the conduct of the study. J.M.S. also reports personal fees from Biocodex, Kyowa Kirin, Norgine, Mayoly Spindler, Precision Biotics, Schär, Tillots, and Reckitt outside the submitted work that do not constitute a conflict of interest in developing the content of the present manuscript. J.S. has served as a consultant for Devintec SAGL, Noventure SL, Reckitt, Ipsen, and Pileje, and discloses present and recent scientific collaborations with Salvat, Norgine, Alfa-Sigma, Cosmo, Adare, Ordesa, and Danone that do not constitute a conflict of interest in developing the content of the present manuscript. The other authors have nothing to declare.

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Supplementary Figure S1. Improvement in stool consistency during the first 15 days of treatment with XP+CS compared to placebo.

Supplementary Table S1. Bristol score summary statistics by days from randomization and treatment period.

Period	Days	Bristol scale	Group 1 (N=30) XP+CS/Placebo	Group 2 (N=30) Placebo/XP+CS	p-value
Period 1	0	1-2	30 (100%)	30 (100%)	-
		3-5	0	0	
	7	1-2	24 (80.0%)	25 (83.3%)	1
		3-5	6 (20.0%)	5 (16.7%)	
	15	1-2	16 (53.3%)	25 (83.3%)	0.04
		3-5	14 (46.7%)	5 (16.7%)	
28	1-2	0	30 (100%)	<0.001	
	3-5	30 (100%)	0		
Period 2	56	1-2	19 (63.3%)	30 (100%)	<0.001
		3-5	11 (36.7%)	0	
	84	1-2	22 (73.3%)	2 (6.7%)	<0.001
		3-5	8 (26.7%)	28 (93.3%)	
Follow-up	114	1-2	27 (90.0%)	10 (33.3%)	<0.001
		3-5	3 (10.0%)	20 (66.7%)	
	144	1-2	24 (80.0%)	15 (50.0%)	0.03
		3-5	6 (20.0%)	15 (50.0%)	

Supplementary Figure S2. Number of patients reporting abdominal pain, bloating, and discomfort (corresponding to Likert values 1-4) according to a 7-point Likert scale (1 = totally unacceptable; 7 = perfectly acceptable). XP+CS treatment reduces the number of IBS-C patients reporting unacceptable levels of abdominal pain (a), bloating (b) and discomfort (c).

Supplementary Table S2. IBS VAS score summary statistics^a by days from randomization and treatment period.

IBS-VAS domain	Period	Days	Group 1 XP+CS/Placebo N = 30	Group 2 Placebo/XP+CS N = 30	p-value ^b
Pain	Period 1	1	33.5 (17.0)	23.0 (8.1)	1.00
		6	70.2 (12.2)	53.8 (12.9)	0.04
		7	75.8 (9.5)	54.8 (14.3)	< 0.001
		15	80.2 (6.7)	55.0 (15.1)	< 0.001
		28	93.2 (3.8)	54.9 (14.8)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	90.2 (4.6)	49.8 (20.0)	< 0.001
		84	68.5 (8.4)	92.3 (3.5)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	69.0 (7.9)	75.0 (9.2)	0.16
		144	60.0 (17.8)	69.9 (12.3)	0.002
	Bloating flatulence	Period 1	1	48.6 (14.5)	35.0 (11.1)
6			85.2 (6.2)	65.8 (11.6)	< 0.001
7			90.8 (4.9)	66.8 (12.2)	< 0.001
15			95.2 (3.8)	67.0 (12.1)	< 0.001
28			99.2 (1.8)	66.9 (12.1)	< 0.001
Period 2		56	89.1 (4.4)	65.9 (11.7)	< 0.001
		84	67.1 (9.1)	87.9 (8.2)	< 0.001
Follow-up		114	52.1 (13.6)	95.9 (3.3)	< 0.001
		144	40.1 (11.3)	83.9 (10.5)	< 0.001
Constipation		Period 1	1	28.4 (8.5)	19.2 (4.9)
	6		65.1 (12.4)	49.9 (17.2)	0.04
	7		70.6 (7.5)	51.0 (16.8)	< 0.001
	15		75.2 (7.8)	57.2 (12.2)	0.001
	28		93.2 (4.3)	63.4 (11.9)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	90.1 (5.3)	59.4 (12.4)	< 0.001
		84	68.6 (9.1)	92.8 (3.4)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	69.0 (8.4)	75.4 (9.0)	0.005
		144	60.0 (15.4)	70.4 (11.3)	< 0.001
	GI Symptoms	Period 1	1	49.6 (21.0)	40.6 (11.9)
6			86.2 (5.2)	71.4 (10.5)	0.002
7			91.8 (5.0)	70.4 (11.2)	< 0.001
15			96.2 (6.2)	72.6 (10.1)	< 0.001
28			99.7 (1.0)	72.5 (10.2)	< 0.001
Period 2		56	80.6 (10.3)	71.6 (10.4)	0.04
		84	65.7 (13.7)	93.5 (3.7)	< 0.001
Follow-up		114	66.2 (13.0)	95.5 (2.7)	< 0.001
		144	64.1 (13.5)	73.1 (12.3)	< 0.001
Psychological well-being		Period 1	1	68.7 (9.3)	53.8 (15.9)
	6		93.4 (3.1)	74.6 (10.5)	< 0.001
	7		98.9 (2.0)	75.6 (9.8)	< 0.001
	15		99.2 (1.8)	73.5 (10.8)	< 0.001
	28		99.4 (1.6)	73.4 (10.1)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	80.4 (8.1)	65.9 (12.3)	< 0.001
		84	65.4 (8.9)	87.9 (6.0)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	50.4 (16.8)	95.9 (3.2)	< 0.001
		144	78.6 (8.5)	83.9 (8.1)	1.00
	Vomiting and nausea	Period 1	1	63.4 (11.2)	43.8 (13.0)
6			88.1 (7.5)	64.6 (10.7)	< 0.001
7			93.6 (6.0)	65.6 (9.8)	< 0.001
15			98.2 (2.8)	63.5 (12.1)	< 0.001
28			98.5 (2.6)	63.4 (12.1)	< 0.001
Period 2		56	79.5 (8.7)	62.4 (11.3)	< 0.001
		84	64.5 (11.1)	84.4 (8.8)	< 0.001
Follow-up		114	69.3 (7.9)	92.4 (6.0)	< 0.001
		144	77.3 (9.3)	80.4 (9.2)	0.06
Diarrhoea		Period 1	1	34.8 (15.7)	23.8 (7.8)
	6		71.5 (12.2)	54.6 (14.3)	0.01

	7	77.0 (8.8)	55.6 (14.3)	< 0.001
	15	82.2 (6.2)	53.5 (14.2)	< 0.001
	28	95.2 (4.3)	53.4 (14.0)	< 0.001
Period 2	56	92.1 (4.8)	48.3 (18.6)	< 0.001
	84	70.1 (7.6)	93.8 (3.9)	< 0.001
Follow-up	114	70.5 (7.6)	76.4 (9.9)	0.23
	144	61.5 (16.3)	71.4 (10.5)	0.002

^a Statistics are Mean (SD); SD = Standard Deviation; ^b Adjusted for multiplicity.

Supplementary Figure S3. Correlation between the VAS-IBS score for constipation and the serum concentration of zonulin in IBS-C patients. Regression analysis plot by days from randomization. r^2 = Pearson's correlation coefficient

Supplementary Table S3. SIP score summary statistics ^a by days from randomization and treatment period.

SIP domain	Period	Days	Group 1 XP+CS/Placebo N = 30	Group 2 Placebo/XP+CS N = 30	p-value ^b
Mobility Range	Period 1	1	2.7 (2,7)	2.7 (0,4)	0.36
		28	1.2 (1,2)	5.4 (3,7)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	4.4 (2,6)	3.1 (0,8)	0.42
		84	6.4 (5,8)	1.4 (0,2)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	2.9 (2,4)	1.1 (0,2)	< 0.001
		144	2.6 (2,3)	1.2 (0,2)	0.01
Social Behavior	Period 1	1	6.5 (4,9)	6.9 (5,8)	1.00
		28	1.1 (0,2)	5.6 (4,7)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	3.7 (2,5)	4.4 (3,5)	1.00
		84	6.9 (5,9)	3.5 (2,5)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	4.2 (3,5)	4.5 (3,6)	1.00
		144	3.9 (2,5)	5.9 (5,7)	< 0.001
Mobility Control	Period 1	1	3.5 (2,5)	2.0 (2,2)	0.41
		28	1.8 (0,3)	5.7 (5,7)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	3.6 (3,5)	6.0 (5,7)	0.009
		84	6.9 (5,8)	2.0 (0,4)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	3.9 (3,5)	5.0 (4,6)	1.00
		144	5.2 (3,7)	6.0 (5,7)	1.00
Somatic Autonomy	Period 1	1	6.5 (4,9)	8.5 (5,11)	0.56
		28	1.1 (0,2)	5.8 (4,8)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	3.7 (2,5)	3.4 (2,4)	1.00
		84	6.9 (5,9)	4.6 (3,6)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	4.2 (3,5)	4.4 (2,7)	1.00
		144	3.9 (2,5)	5.4 (3,8)	0.50
Emotional Stability	Period 1	1	3.3 (2,4)	2.7 (2,4)	1.00
		28	2.4 (2,3)	1.7 (1,3)	1.00
	Period 2	56	2.4 (2,3)	3.1 (2,4)	0.14
		84	2.1 (1,3)	4.2 (3,6)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	2.2 (1,3)	3.2 (2,5)	0.09
		144	2.5 (2,3)	2.2 (2, 3)	1.00
Psychological Autonomy	Period 1	1	6.5 (4,9)	6.9 (5,8)	1.00
		28	1.1 (0,2)	5.6 (4,7)	< 0.001
	Period 2	56	3.7 (2,5)	4.4 (3,5)	1.00
		84	6.9 (5,9)	3.5 (2,5)	< 0.001
	Follow-up	114	4.2 (3,5)	4.5 (3,6)	1.00
		144	3.9 (2,5)	5.9 (5,7)	< 0.001

^a Statistics are Mean (IQR); IQR = Interquartile Range; ^b Adjusted for multiplicity.

Supplementary Figure S4. Study flowchart.

